

The exact probability of an event

Ilija Barukčić¹*

¹Internist, Horandstr., DE-26441 Jever, Germany / Published online: 3.9.2023

Abstract. Background: This study delves into the intricate relationship between Chebyshev's inequality and the probability of an event, shedding light on how mathematics provides insights into the likelihood of events across various distributions. **Methods:** In this study, we start by providing a comprehensive overview of Chebyshev's inequality, elucidating its formulation and inherent characteristics. We then delve into the theoretical foundation of event probability, presenting the mathematical framework that quantifies the likelihood of an event occurring within a given dataset. By combining elaborating on these two concepts, we develop a novel approach that provide us with the exact probability of an event. **Results:** Our investigation reveals that Chebyshev's inequality provides only an upper limit on the probability of an event occurring, contingent on the number of standard deviations from the mean within which the event resides. As the number of standard deviations increases, the bound on the event probability tightens, presenting a conservative estimate that holds true for diverse datasets. This result is particularly significant in scenarios where the underlying distribution lacks well-defined characteristics or is not normally distributed. **Conclusions:** In conclusion, this study illuminates the dynamic relationship between variance and the probability of an event.

1. Introduction

Chebyshev's [1] inequality, also known as Chebyshev's theorem or the Bienaymé–Chebyshev inequality, is named after “the founding father of Russian mathematics”, Pafnuty Lvovich Chebyshev (1821 – 1894). However, this theorem has been first stated without a proof by Bienaymé [2] in 1853 and has been proved later by Chebyshev himself in 1867. Meanwhile, Chebyshev's inequality is a widely used mathematical concept especially in probability theory and statistics. This inequality provides a way to estimate the proportion of data that falls within a certain number of standard deviations from the mean of a distribution, regardless of the distribution's shape. Chebyshev's theorem is a powerful tool for understanding the spread of data in a general sense which is not assuming any specific properties about the distribution. Thus far, let $\mathbb{R}X_t$ denote a random

* Corresponding author: ibarukcic@yandex.com

variable [3] with a finite non-zero variance $\sigma(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2$, let $E(\mathbb{R}X_t)$ denote a finite expected value $E(\mathbb{R}X_t)$ of the random variable $\mathbb{R}X_t$. For any real number $\sqrt[2]{E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2)} > 0$, it is

$$p\left(\left|\mathbb{R}X_t - E(\mathbb{R}X_t)\right| \geq \sqrt[2]{E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2)}\right) \leq \frac{\sigma(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2}{E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2)} \quad (1)$$

while the complementary event is given as

$$p\left(\left|\mathbb{R}X_t - E(\mathbb{R}X_t)\right| < \sqrt[2]{E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2)}\right) \geq 1 - \frac{\sigma(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2}{E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2)} \quad (2)$$

In point of fact, Chebyshev's inequality can be applied to any distribution, making it a versatile tool when dealing with distributions that might not follow a normal distribution. At the same time, Chebyshev's inequality provides a very conservative estimate of the proportion of data within a certain range. This means it gives an upper bound on the proportion of data that falls within the specified range, which can be useful for worst-case scenario analysis. In brief, especially when the distribution is not strongly concentrated around the mean, Chebyshev's inequality tends to some extent to give a loose bound on the proportion of data within the specified range with the sometimes disastrous consequence that the estimated proportion might be significantly larger than the actual proportion of data within the range. Chebyshev's inequality, even if useful in various scenarios might lack an appropriate precision. When dealing with specific distributions, especially those with known properties like the normal distribution, more precise methods can provide more accurate estimates of the proportion of data within a given range than Chebyshev's inequality. However, in finance, economics, stock exchange et cetera, Chebyshev's inequality is still applied to help us to identify potential outliers in a dataset by quantifying how far data points are from the mean in terms of standard deviations.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Definitions

Definitions in mathematics are the foundation upon which an entire mathematical framework is constructed. Definitions provide us with the necessary language and rules of mathematics, enabling the development of theorems, proofs, and the systematic exploration of mathematical ideas, allowing scientists and mathematicians to communicate and reason effectively. However, definitions can be incorrect if they are not carefully formulated or if they lead to contradictions or inconsistencies. An incorrect definition can result in misinterpretation, flawed reasoning, and erroneous conclusions. More or less, in mathematics the correctness of a definition is typically established through logical analysis and consistency checking. In contrast to theorems, which can be proven, definitions are more about establishing meaning and understanding.

2.1.1. Random variable

A (random) variable ${}_R X_t$ at a specific time instance t is defined as a set (or sample space) that encompasses all possible distinct outcomes or events of a random experiment (state of super-position). In this representation, each single element of ${}_R X_t$ (e.g., $x_{t0}, x_{t1}, x_{t2}, \dots$) is itself a subset of ${}_R X_t$, denoting a specific and mutually exclusive event or outcome associated with ${}_R X_t$. Mathematically, we obtain:

$$+{}_R X_t = +\{x_{t0}, x_{t1}, x_{t2}, \dots\} \quad (3)$$

or in the negative as

$$-{}_R X_t = -\{x_{t0}, x_{t1}, x_{t2}, \dots\} \quad (4)$$

Each ${}_i x_t$ represents a specific event within the set ${}_R X_t$ which itself is a set of subsets. In contrast to the definition before, in the context of probability theory, a random variable is a function that assigns real numbers to outcomes in a sample space and is not directly represented as a set of elements, but rather as a mapping from the sample space to the real numbers.

2.1.2. Expectation value

The expected value of a (random) variable ${}_R X_t$ at a specific time instance t , denoted as $E({}_R X_t)$, is defined as a set that encompasses all possible distinct expectation values associated with ${}_R X_t$. Each individual expectation value as a subset within $E({}_R X_t)$, denoted by $E(x_{t0}^2), E(x_{t1}^2), E(x_{t2}^2), \dots$, represents the expected value associated with a specific event or outcome of ${}_R X_t$. Mathematically, we obtain:

$$+E({}_R X_t) = +\{E(x_{t0}^2), E(x_{t1}^2), E(x_{t2}^2), \dots\} \quad (5)$$

or in the negative as

$$-E({}_R X_t) = -\{E(x_{t0}^2), E(x_{t1}^2), E(x_{t2}^2), \dots\} \quad (6)$$

2.1.3. Expectation of squared value

The expected value of a squared (random) variable ${}_R X_t$ at a specific time instance t , denoted as $E({}_R X_t^2)$, is defined as a set that encompasses all possible distinct expectation

values associated with ${}_R X_t^2$. Each individual expectation value as a subset within $E({}_R X_t^2)$, denoted by $E(x_{t0}^2), E(x_{t1}^2), E(x_{t2}^2), \dots$, represents the expected value associated with a specific event or outcome of ${}_R X_t^2$. Mathematically, we obtain:

$$+E({}_R X_t^2) = +\{E(x_{t0}^2), E(x_{t1}^2), E(x_{t2}^2), \dots\} \quad (7)$$

or in the negative as

$$-E({}_R X_t^2) = -\{E(x_{t0}^2), E(x_{t1}^2), E(x_{t2}^2), \dots\} \quad (8)$$

2.1.4. Probability

Let P denote a set of all possible probabilities within the closed interval [0,1]. This is expressed as in the positive as

$$+P = +[0,1] \quad (9)$$

or in the negative as

$$-P = -[0,1] \quad (10)$$

The probability of a (random) variable ${}_R X_t$ at a specific time instance t, denoted as $p({}_R X_t)$, is defined by the relationship

$$p({}_R X_t) = \frac{E({}_R X_t)}{{}_R X_t} \quad (11)$$

or in the negative as

$$-p({}_R X_t) = -\frac{E({}_R X_t)}{{}_R X_t} \quad (12)$$

It is

$$1-p({}_R X_t) = 1 - \frac{E({}_R X_t)}{{}_R X_t} \quad (13)$$

The probability of the other, of the complementary, of the opposite et cetera of a (random) variable ${}_R X_t$ at a specific time instance t, denoted as $p({}_R \underline{X}_t)$, is defined by the relationship

$$p({}_R \underline{X}_t) = 1-p({}_R X_t) = 1 - \frac{E({}_R X_t)}{{}_R X_t} = \frac{{}_R X_t - E({}_R X_t)}{{}_R X_t} \quad (14)$$

The probability of a single event is given as

$$p(x_{ti}) = \frac{E(x_{ti})}{x_{ti}} \quad (15)$$

or in the negative as

$$-p(x_{ti}) = -\frac{E(x_{ti})}{x_{ti}} \quad (16)$$

A probability triple, also known as a probability space, consists of three fundamental components known as the sample space, the event space and the probability measure which form the basis of probability theory. In this alternative approach to probability theory, the so called probability triple is determined by the (random) variable itself and its own expectation value while both regulate their inner relationship via probability (see equation 11).

2.1.5. Variance

The variance [3] of a (random) variable ${}_R X_t$ at a specific time instance t , denoted as $\sigma({}_R X_t)^2$, is defined as a set that encompasses all possible distinct variances associated with ${}_R X_t$. In the positive, we obtain

$$\sigma({}_R X_t)^2 = E({}_R X_t^2) - E({}_R X_t)^2 \quad (17)$$

or in the negative as

$$-\sigma({}_R X_t)^2 = -E({}_R X_t^2) + E({}_R X_t)^2 \quad (18)$$

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Axiom I (*Lex Identitatis*)

Axiom I, the Axiom of Identity or *lex identitatis*, introduces the concept of equality and sameness within scientific or mathematical discourse as

$$+1 = +1 \quad (19)$$

or in the negative as

$$-1 = -1 \quad (20)$$

This axiom, while seemingly trivial, embodies a fundamental concept that underpins the very essence of arithmetic and mathematical reasoning. By embracing this fundamental equality, mathematical reasoning retains its logical rigor and allows for the development of more intricate mathematical structures. The equation $+1=+1$, grounded in Axiom I, showcases the consistency that this axiom lends to mathematical systems. Often

overlooked due to its apparent simplicity, the philosophical underpinnings and mathematical significance of Axiom I deserves a meticulous examination in order to illuminate its far reaching role in shaping scientific and mathematical structures. Although Axiom I's embodiment in an equation as basic as $+1=+1$ finds its roots in arithmetic, its implications extend far beyond this realm. It serves as the cornerstone of scientific and mathematical equivalence, permeating disciplines ranging from philosophy, algebra to analysis, and beyond into more advanced branches of mathematics, science and philosophy. Axiom I intersects with philosophical notions of identity and existence. The equation $+1=+1$ mirrors the axiom's assertion that an entity is unequivocally identical to itself, invoking contemplation about the nature of scientific and mathematical entities and their existence within abstract realms.

2.2.2. Axiom II (*Lex contradictionis*)

Axiom II, the Axiom of Contradiction or *lex contradictionis*, introduces the concept of difference, opposition and contradiction et cetera within scientific or mathematical discourse as

$$+0 = +1 \tag{21}$$

or in the negative as

$$-0 = -1 \tag{22}$$

This axiom, while seemingly trivial too, is a fundamental concept which underpins the other side of any arithmetic and mathematical or scientific reasoning, the possibility to make an error. Nonetheless, it is important to note that this principle is not used to derive meaningful or valid theorems in standard mathematics and in science as such. In this context the logical consequence of this Axiom would indeed be that any proposition, no matter how unrelated, can be proven true, which could lead to a breakdown of logical consistency. The main task of Axiom II is to preserve at all cost the contradiction, the falsity et cetera. In other words, a chain of logic which starts with a contradiction, must end up at the contradiction, the contradiction must be persevered. Otherwise, there is an error somewhere in the chain of reasoning or a negation. Axiom II highlights the logical impact of contradictions and serves as a cautionary tool to check theorems for consistent and coherent logical reasoning and is of help to maintain the logical integrity of mathematical theories and theorems. In contrast to Axiom II (*lex contradictionis*), which demands that the contradiction must be preserved, ***the Principle of Explosion***, often expressed by the Latin phrase "*ex falso quodlibet*" (from falsehood, anything follows), allows and demands that any proposition can be proven true from a contradiction.

2.2.3.Axiom III (Lex negationis)

The Axiom of Negation asserts the existence of a natural process, a logical operation et cetera denoted as negation. The Axiom of Negation that for anything existing, there exists a negation, such that both are mutually exclusive and their combination results in a logically consistent outcome. In mathematics and classical logic, negation is given in the positive as as

$$+(\neg) \times (+0) = +1 \quad (23)$$

or in the negative as

$$-(\neg) \times (+0) = -1 \quad (24)$$

while $(\neg)$ denotes the process of negation. This axiom lays the groundwork for constructing logical systems that adhere to the principles of classical logic, enabling the development of coherent and consistent mathematical theories and theorems. It's important to note that the Axiom of Negation is widely accepted and used in mathematical and philosophical contexts, providing a foundational element for logical reasoning and deduction.

3. Results

3.1.Theorem 1. The probability of an event

Claim.

The probability of a (random) variable ${}_R X_t$ is given as

$$p({}_R X_t) = +1 - \frac{\sigma({}_R X_t)^2}{E({}_R X_t^2)} \quad (25)$$

Proof.

The variance is defined as (see equation 17)

$$\sigma({}_R X_t)^2 = E({}_R X_t^2) - E({}_R X_t)^2 \quad (26)$$

Rearranging equation, we obtain

$$E({}_R X_t^2) = E({}_R X_t)^2 + \sigma({}_R X_t)^2 \quad (27)$$

or as

$$\frac{E({}_R X_t)^2}{E({}_R X_t^2)} + \frac{\sigma({}_R X_t)^2}{E({}_R X_t^2)} = +1 \quad (28)$$

Equation 28 is equivalent with the relationship

$$\frac{({}_R X_t) \times p({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t) \times p({}_R X_t)}{({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t) \times p({}_R X_t)} + \frac{\sigma({}_R X_t)^2}{E({}_R X_t^2)} = +1 \quad (29)$$

Equation 29 simplifies as

$$p({}_R X_t) + \frac{\sigma({}_R X_t)^2}{E({}_R X_t^2)} = +1 \quad (30)$$

In general, it is

$$p({}_R X_t) = +1 - \frac{\sigma({}_R X_t)^2}{E({}_R X_t^2)} \quad (31)$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.

Chebyshev's inequality provides an upper bound on the probability that a random variable deviates from its mean by a certain amount. However and in contrast to Chebyshev's inequality, equation 31 provide us with an exact probability of a specific event, without a typically need of additional information about the distribution of the random variable, such as its probability distribution function (PDF) or cumulative distribution function (CDF) et cetera.

An ordered set of events in time is often referred to as a time series. A time series is a sequence of events, measurements, or data points in which the order and the temporal spacing between events are crucial. Time series data is commonly used in various scientific disciplines and applications, including weather forecasting, signal processing, finance, and more. **Example.** The exact probability of an event [4,5] during the last $t=365$ data points, denoted as $p({}_R X_{t=365})$, would be

$$p({}_R X_{t=365}) = +1 - \frac{\sigma({}_R X_{t=365})^2}{E({}_R X_{t=365}^2)} \quad (32)$$

where $\sigma({}_R X_{t=365})^2$ is the variance during the last $t=365$ data points and ${}_R X_{t=365}^2$ is the expectation of the squared value of ${}_R X_t$ during the last $t=365$ data points. By examining how probabilities change over data points or over time, it becomes possible to make forecasts or predictions about future probabilities. Studying the probabilities of an event over the time axis or over certain data points, often referred to as analysing a time series of probabilities, offers other possibilities too. Analysing probabilities over time enhances decision-making, risk management, and understanding of dynamic systems in various fields, offering valuable insights for informed actions and strategies. Time series analysis of probabilities is used in scientific research to study various phenomena, from disease spread to ecological changes. Understanding how probabilities evolve provides insights into underlying processes.

3.2.Theorem 2. The mean value and the probability of an event

Claim.

The probability of a (random) variable ${}_R X_t$ is given as

$$p({}_R X_t) = +1 - \frac{\sigma\left({}_R \bar{X}_t\right)^2}{E\left({}_R \bar{X}_t^2\right)} \tag{33}$$

Proof.

The probability of a (random) variable ${}_R X_t$ is given (see equation 31) as

$$p({}_R X_t) = +1 - \frac{\sigma\left({}_R X_t\right)^2}{E\left({}_R X_t^2\right)} \tag{34}$$

Let N denote the size of a population. We obtain that

$$p({}_R X_t) = +1 - \left(\left(\frac{\frac{1}{N} \times \sigma\left({}_R X_t\right)^2}{1} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\frac{1}{N} \times E\left({}_R X_t^2\right)} \right) \right) \tag{35}$$

and equally

$$p({}_R X_t) = +1 - \left(\left(\frac{\sigma\left({}_R X_t\right)^2}{N} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\frac{1}{N} \times E\left({}_R X_t^2\right)} \right) \right) \tag{36}$$

The relationship between the standard error of the mean and the standard deviation for a given population size N is such that

$$\sigma\left({}_R \bar{X}_t\right) = \left(\frac{\sigma\left({}_R X_t\right)}{\sqrt[2]{N}} \right) \tag{37}$$

Equation 36 becomes

$$p({}_R X_t) = +1 - \frac{\sigma\left({}_R \bar{X}_t\right)^2}{\frac{E\left({}_R X_t^2\right)}{N}} \tag{38}$$

Using the equivalence of

$$E\left({}_R \bar{X}_t^2\right) = \left(\frac{E\left({}_R X_t^2\right)}{N} \right) \tag{39}$$

Equation 38 becomes

$$p({}_R X_t) = +1 - \frac{\sigma\left({}_R \bar{X}_t\right)^2}{E\left({}_R \bar{X}_t^2\right)} \tag{40}$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.

To calculate probabilities associated with specific events or outcomes, the probability distribution of the random variable is needed typically. This distribution considers the relative frequencies of each outcome and their probabilities. However, it is reasonable to assume that even the mean of a random variable itself does directly provide the probabilities of specific events without the need of the probability distribution of the random variable for such calculations. Nonetheless, we need the variance. Under the circumstances before, the expectation of the squared mean of the random variable ${}_R X_t$ is given as

$$E\left({}_R \bar{X}_t^2\right) = \sum_{t=+1}^N \frac{({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t)}{N} \quad (41)$$

and the mean itself would follow as

$$E\left({}_R \bar{X}_t\right) = \sum_{t=+1}^N \frac{({}_R X_t)}{N} \quad (42)$$

The variance becomes under these circumstances

$$\sigma\left({}_R \bar{X}_t\right)^2 = \left(\sum_{t=+1}^N \frac{({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t)}{N}\right) - \left(\sum_{t=+1}^N \frac{({}_R X_t)}{N}\right)^2 \quad (43)$$

The formulas are based on the population size and need to be adopted for a sample size. As known, the more a sample size increases, the more the mean of the random variable becomes reliable and tends to converge to the true population mean.

4. Discussion

In summary, Chebyshev's inequality is indeed simple to use and broadly applicable tool for estimating the proportion of data within a specified range from the mean of any distribution. While it has its advantages in its generality and conservative estimates, its loose bounds and lack of precision can limit its usefulness in situations where more specific distributional information is available. While Chebyshev's inequality certainly has its merits and can be valuable in certain contexts, there are scenarios where its limitations might prompt researchers or practitioners to consider alternative approaches like Markov's [6] inequality, Chernoff [7] inequality, Hoeffding [8] inequality et cetera, which can provide tighter bounds under specific conditions. These inequalities might be more suitable for certain applications where the assumptions of Chebyshev's inequality are not met. However, even these inequalities have their limitations and potential drawbacks too. The Markov inequality provides a very general bound on the tail probabilities of non-negative random variables. However, it might not be the tightest

bound in all cases. Chernoff bounds often involve complex exponentials and algebraic manipulations, which can be computationally intensive for large sample sizes or complex distributions. Hoeffding's inequality is most effective when applied to bounded random variables. When dealing with unbounded variables, the bounds might be unnecessarily conservative. Selecting the appropriate inequality can be challenging, as it often depends on the specific problem, the characteristics of the random variables, and the desired level of precision. It's not always clear which inequality will provide the best results. Despite these limitations, the Markov, Chernoff, and Hoeffding inequalities remain valuable tools in various statistical applications. However, it's important to be aware of the possibilities provided by this publication. In the meantime, we have access to new statistical techniques which allow us to precisely compute the probability of an event. In this context, the previous inequalities do not lose their entire significance; instead, they take on a relative importance.

5. Conclusion

Fresh methods that enable us to accurately calculate event probabilities will enhance our scientific capabilities and make our lives more convenient.

References

1. P. L. Tschébychef, *Journal de Mathématiques Pures et Appliquées* **12**, 177 (1867).
2. I.-J. Bienaymé, *Comptes Rendus Des Séances de l'Académie Des Sciences Des Paris* **37**, 309 (1853).
3. A. Kolmogoroff, *Grundbegriffe Der Wahrscheinlichkeitsrechnung* (Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1933).
4. I. Barukčić, *MATEC Web Conf.* **336**, 09032 (2021).
5. I. Barukčić, *IJAPM* **6**, 45 (2016).
6. A. A. Markov, *Изчисление Вероятностей (Ischislenie Veroiatnostei; Calculus of Probabilities)* (Gosizdat, Moscow, 1913).
7. H. Chernoff, *Ann. Probab.* **9**, 533 (1981).
8. W. Hoeffding, *Journal of the American Statistical Association* **58**, 13 (1963).